

DEHYDROGENASE ACTIVITY AND INORGANIC SUBSTRATES

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The mechanism of oxidation process by dehydrogenases has so far been investigated almost only with organic substrates such as glucose, succinic acid, xanthine, lactic acid etc. There are, however, oxidations *in vivo* where the energy liberated by inorganic chemical processes serve to raise the energy potential of carbon dioxide in the assimilation process. Among these may be mentioned the oxidation of ammonia, nitrite, sulphur, hydrogen sulphide etc., by the respective chemosynthesising autotrophic bacteria.

According to Wieland (*Ergeb. Physiol.*, 1922, 20, 477) a great majority of biological oxidations is essentially dehydrogenations and practically all oxidations of organic compounds *in vivo* actually produce a loss of hydrogen atoms. It has been shown by the author (*Biochem. Z.*, 1939, 300, 122; *Science*, 1936, 84, 440) that the biological oxidation of ammonia by the nitrosobacteria does not involve an activation of hydrogen and that ammonia never becomes a hydrogen donor in the presence of organisms known to possess dehydrogenase activity. It was also made clear that nitrifiers lacked the power of activating the hydrogen of any given organic substrate.

The question thus arose whether the incapacity of organisms of established dehydrogenase activity to activate inorganic hydrogen was a general property of the group. Preliminary experiments, now completed with a view to elucidating the mechanism of oxidation by autotrophic agencies in inorganic substrates, and that by heterotrophic systems in organic substrates, show that dehydrogenases procured from various well known sources are incapable of hydrogen activation so long as the hydrogen is in inorganic combination.

TABLE I

Temperature, 37° in all cases.

No.	Source of the dehydrogenase. 2 c.c. of the enzyme present in phosphate buffer (pH 8)	Substrates, 2 c.c. <i>M</i> /140 each Omeliansky soln. 2 c.c.	Rate of reduction of 0.00034 <i>M</i> Methylene blue.
1.	<i>B. coli</i>	{ Glucose solution Omeliansky solution Ammonium carbonate solution	+ + + - - - - - -
2.	<i>Azotobacter</i>	{ Glucose solution Omeliansky solution Ammonium carbonate solution	+ + + - - - - - -

No.	Source of the dehydrogenase. 2c.c. of the enzyme present in phosphate buffer (pH 8)	Substrates 2c.c. $M/140$ each Omeliansky soln. 2 c.c.	Rate of reduction of 0.0034M Methylene blue
3.	Succinoxidase from muscle	Sodium succinate solution	+ + +
		Omeliansky solution	— — —
		Ammonium carbonate solution	— — —
4.	Xanthine oxidase from milk	Hypoxanthine solution	+ + +
		Omeliansky solution	— — —
		Ammonium carbonate solution	— — —
5.	Xanthine oxidase from liver	Hypoxanthine solution	+ + +
		Omeliansky solution	— — —
		Ammonium carbonate solution	— — —
6.	Lactic oxidase from yeast	Lactate solution	+ + +
		Omeliansky solution	— — —
		Ammonium carbonate solution	— — —
	+ + +	indicates rapid decolorisation	
	— — —	indicates no decolorisation	

A solution of pure ammonium carbonate and a solution of the well known culture medium of the Nitrosobacteria of Omeliansky (*Centrl Bakt.*, 1902, II, 9, 63, 113) were among the chief inorganic substrates investigated in these experiments. The simultaneous use of the appropriate organic substrates served as reliable controls. The Tunberg technique adopted in previous studies was preferred here also in all details. The point was also made clear that Omeliansky solution or ammonium carbonate in the concentrations used were without effect on the dehydrogenase action of the enzymes studied in their respective substrates.

Various conditions of pH, temperature, and concentration of enzymes and substrates were studied. It would thus seem that dehydrogenase activity is a feature associated only with organisms of the saprophytic group, others of a more primordial type as the autrophic [nitrite-formers entirely devoid of chlorophyll or any photodynamic pigment functioning by different mechanisms. The question of activation of inorganic hydrogen by dehydrogenases and organic hydrogen by chemosynthesising bacteria is being pursued in fuller detail.